

Xylenol Orange. An Amperometric Reagent for Trace Estimation of Erbium(III), Terbium(III) and Dysprosium(III)

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Xylenol orange has been successfully employed as an amperometric reagent for precise estimation of some rare earths. Amperometric titration were performed at -1.10 V vs Hg pool, $pH=6.50$, ionic strength $\mu=0.3$ and temperature $=70 \pm 1^\circ$. The molar ratio of metal-xylenol orange complexation is found to be 1:1. Spectrophotometric studies also confirmed the said ratio. Titrations are not hampered by the presence of fairly large amount of K^+ , Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , ammonium, Co^{2+} , Mo^{6+} , chloride and chlorate ions. The experimental and calculated statistical data support the utility of the method and report the accuracy and precision of the procedure adopted.

LAVALLE and Pitre¹ have used xylenol orange for amperometric estimation of rare earths. The dye has been used as a spectrophotometric², complexometric³ and pH-metric⁴ reagent for the estimation of various metal ions. In continuation to the work in our laboratory on microgram and ultramicrogram estimation of rare earths using the amperometric titration technique, the present paper reports the results of amperometric titration of Er^{3+} , Tb^{3+} and Dy^{3+} with xylenol orange.

Experimental

The chemical used were of AnalaR quality. Solution of rare earths, Er^{3+} , Tb^{3+} and Dy^{3+} were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of the rare earth nitrate in double-distilled water and standardised⁵. The solution of xylenol orange was prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of the reagent (B.D.H.) in conductivity water. Amperometric titrations were made on a manually operated polarograph with a multiflex galvanometer (sensitivity 8.10×10^{-9} A/div) to measure the current. A d.m.e. and a S.C.E. were used as an indicator and reference electrode, respectively. The capillary used for d.m.e. had the following characteristics, $m=2.3733$ mg/sec, $t=3.0$ sec at 41 cm effective height of mercury column ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.316$ $mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}$). An Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used for measuring the pH of the test solutions. The amperometric titrations were performed at $70 \pm 1^\circ$ maintained on a thermostat.

Polarogram of xylenol orange: Xylenol orange gave a well defined double reduction¹⁰ polarographic wave (Fig. 1A) at $pH=6.0 \pm 0.02$ and $temp.=70 \pm 1^\circ$ with $E_{1/2} = -0.90$ V vs Hg pool and -1.10 V vs Hg pool, respectively. The diffusion current for both the waves was proportional to the concentration of xylenol orange.

Fig. 1. (A) Polarogram of 1 mM xylenol orange in 0.3 M KCl at $pH=6.0$, (B) Polarogram of 2 mM Er^{3+} in 0.3 M KCl at $pH=6.0$.

Procedure of amperometric titration: For titrations, sets of solutions containing known amount of xylenol orange in 0.3 M KCl as supporting electrolyte were prepared and pH of the solutions was adjusted at 6.0 ± 0.02 with B.R. buffer⁶. The plateau potential for the second wave was applied and a standard solution of rare earth was added drop by drop from a 1 cm³ semimicro burette and the current was noted. On plotting a graph between galvanometer deflection after necessary volume correction against titrant volume, an L shaped curve was obtained (Fig. 2). The end point of titration indicated a metal to ligand ratio of 1:1 which is in good agreement with the results reported in the literature⁷. Reversed L shaped curve may be obtained by taking xylenol orange as titrant and metal as a titrate.

Effect of diverse ions: The amperometric titration of the titled rare earths was not any way hampered by the presence of fairly large amount

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Er^{III}, Tb^{III} AND Dy^{III} WITH XYLENOL ORANGE

Sl no.	Approximate concentration <i>M</i>	Amount of Er ^{III}			Amount of Tb ^{III}			Amount of Dy ^{III}		
		taken mg	found mg	Error %	taken mg	found mg	Error %	taken mg	found mg	Error %
1.	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.1670	0.1657	-0.75	0.1589	0.1573	-0.38	0.1625	0.1613	-0.74
2.	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.4125	0.4136	+0.15	0.3973	0.3985	+0.32	0.4625	0.4658	+0.71
3.	5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.8035	0.8047	+0.19	0.7946	0.7920	-0.31	0.8125	0.8110	-0.19
4.	7.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.2525	1.2500	-0.19	1.1919	1.1931	+0.10	1.2750	1.2729	-0.15
5.	1.0 × 10 ⁻³	1.6700	1.6731	+0.18	1.5892	1.5860	-0.21	1.6250	1.6280	+0.17
6.	1.5 × 10 ⁻³	2.4735	2.4758	+0.9	2.3838	2.3830	+0.16	2.4375	2.4348	-0.18
7.	2.0 × 10 ⁻³	3.340	3.310	-0.89	3.1948	3.1951	-0.16	3.250	3.2750	+0.76
		AMD = 0.348 SD = 0.283 CV = 0.807			AMD = 0.332 SD = 0.253 CV = 0.704			AMD = 0.415 SD = 0.261 CV = 0.682		

AMD = Average mean deviation, SD = Standard deviation, CV = Coefficient of variation.

Fig 2. Amperometric titration curve of xylenol orange with Er^{III} at pH=6.0, $\mu=0.3$ M KCl and plateau potential = -1.10 vs S.C.E., temp. = 70 ± 1°: (Δ) 0.5 mM × 0 titrated against 5 mM Er^{III} solution; (○) 0.75 mM × 0 titrated against 7.5 mM Er^{III} solution; (●) 1.0 mM × 0 titrated against 10 mM Er^{III} solution.

of foreign ions, viz. alkali and alkaline earth metals, Ti²⁺, Cr^{VI}, Mo^{VI}, ammonium, chlorate, nitrate, sulphate, acetate, etc. However, it is found that a small amount of Pd^{II}, Bi^{III}, Pb^{II}, Sb^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, carbonate and phosphate interfered seriously in the titration procedure.

Absorption studies on complexation: Vosburg and Copper's method⁹ was used to study the metal-ligand complexation. The visible absorption spectra of 1 × 10⁻⁴ M xylenol orange at pH=6.0 ± 0.02 consist of a single maximum at 575 mμ (Fig. 3). The shift in λ_{max} is attributed to the formation of complex under varying mixing ratios. The stoichiometry of complex was studied by applying Job's method⁹ of continuous variation at pH 6.0 ± 0.02 and wave length 680 mμ (Fig. 3). A double beam sample chamber GCA/MCPHERSON EU AU 707-11 spectrophotometer was used for the absorp-

tion studies. The stoichiometry and formation constant of the complex were determined by preparing sets of solutions containing varying concentrations of metal and ligand. The pH of each set was fixed at 6.0 ± 0.02. The spectrophotometric studies indicated 1 : 1 ratio of the titled rare earths with xylenol orange. The value of log conditional formation constant for Er^{III}-xylenol orange is 11.9 in solution.

Fig. 3. Job's plot for composition at 680 mμ.

Accuracy and precision: Table 1 represents the results of amperometric titration of Er^{III}, Tb^{III} and Dy^{III} with xylenol orange. Ultramicro and microgram quantities of the titled rare earths could be successfully estimated amperometrically with an error of less than ± 0.8%.

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